

Influence of Independent and Simultaneous Additions of Potassium and Starch or Rice Straw on N-Availability and NH_4^+ Fixation in Limed and Unlimed Soils

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In general a higher amount of clay fixed ammonium and lower amount of exchangeable ammonium were observed in the limed over the unlimed soil. Irrespective of liming and organic matter treatments, much lower amount of clay fixed NH_4^+ was noted in the starch added soil. Starch addition promoted heterotrophic microbes to utilise considerable amount of fixed NH_4^+ resulting stress for available N in the soil system. In absence of added ammonium no effect of added potassium was observed in limed soil. But much lower amount of fixed NH_4^+ was observed in both the limed and unlimed soil due to added potassium when simultaneously present with ammonium in starch added soil.

THE depressive effect of K^+ on the fixation of NH_4^+ is well known and has been demonstrated by several workers¹⁻⁴. However, considerable inconsistencies exist regarding the fixation of NH_4^+ in limed soil in that the NH_4^+ produced through increased mineralisation of soil organic nitrogen in the limed soil can also serve as source of clay-fixed NH_4^+ which is appreciably governed by microbial activity of the soil. Due to favourable environment under the limed as compared to the corresponding unlimed soil, higher microbial activity would be expected, and therefore, the fixation and release of fixed NH_4^+ would likely to vary in these soils. Indeed, simultaneous addition of K^+ and organic matter of wide C/N ratio to such soils is not an uncommon practice.

Hence, the present investigation was conducted to study the effect of added K^+ with and without starch or rice straw treatment on the release of recently fixed NH_4^+ by limed and the corresponding unlimed soil.

Experimental

The soil selected for the present investigation was collected from 0-15 cm layer of Bagdubi village in Midnapore, West Bengal; the pH, 5.4; organic C, 0.55%; total N, 0.071%; W.H.C., 51%; C.E.C., 7.84 me/100 g; clay, 39%, dominant clay mineral, illite; exchangeable NH_4^+ , 35; soluble NO_3^- , 14; native fixed NH_4^+ , 514; NH_4^+ -fixing capacity of soil, 1079 ppm. The soil used in the present investigation was under Loamy skeletal mixed hyperthermic family of Plinthustalfs as per U.S.D.A. Soil Taxonomy. After collection, the soil was air-dried and crushed to pass through 0.5 mm sieve.

Liming soils of acidic reaction preceded the actual incubation experiment. The procedure adopted for liming operation has been described previously⁵.

Thus prepared unlimed and limed soils were incubated with the following treatments.

- (i) Control, where no source of nitrogen and organic matter was added.
- (ii) Treatment (i) + 200 ppm K added through KCl.
- (iii) Treatment (ii) + starch added at the rate of 0.5% of the soil (w/w).
- (iv) Treatment (ii) + rice straw (N, 1.20%) added at the rate of 1% of the soil (w/w).
- (v) Treatment (i) + starch added at the rate of 0.5% of the soil (w/w) + 400 ppm N added through $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$.
- (vi) Treatment (i) + rice straw (N, 1.20%) added at the rate of 1% of the soil (w/w) + 400 ppm N added through $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$.
- (vii) Treatment (v) + 200 ppm K added through KCl.
- (viii) Treatment (vi) + 200 ppm K added through KCl.

Experimental details of the treated soil samples have been described previously⁵⁻⁷.

Results and Discussion

Irrespective of treatments, in general, lower amount of exchangeable NH_4^+ was recorded in the soils collected on both the 5th. and 15th. day stage of

incubation in the limed than in the unlimed conditions (Tables 1 and 2). However, no variation between limed and unlimed soils was noticed in the starch+K and rice straw+K treatment added samples of 5th. day. Favourable pH created due to liming soils of acidic reaction increased the activity of the heterotrophic microbes. This resulted in a higher amount of utilisation of the available nitrogen in the form of exchangeable NH_4^+ , thereby leading to its lower content under limed condition. Among the inorganic N-forms investigated, NO_3^- -N was found to be present in very small amount (Tables 1 and 2) as compared to the corresponding amount of exchangeable NH_4^+ -N and fixed NH_4^+ -N. Marked changes in the amount of soluble NO_3^- -N was not observed due to any of the added treatments. This may be a reflection of its small content in the soil system. However, when the sum of the amount of exchangeable NH_4^+ -N and soluble NO_3^- -N as an estimate of available N was taken into consideration, the result indicated treatment responses similar to what was observed for exchangeable NH_4^+ -N. Changes occurred in the amount of exchangeable NH_4^+ -N and soluble NO_3^- -N during incubation may possibly be the direct result of the changes in the activity of the heterotrophic and nitrifying microorganisms in the soil following addition of the treatment materials.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF ADDED POTASSIUM ON CHANGES IN THE AMOUNT (ppm) OF MINERAL FORMS OF N DURING INCUBATION IN LIMED AND UNLIMED SOIL, TREATED WITH AND WITHOUT ORGANIC MATTER

Treatment material added to soil	Lime treatment	Amount of forms of the nitrogen in soil					
		5th. day			15th. day		
		Exch. NH_4^+	Soluble NO_3^-	Fixed NH_4^+	Exch. NH_4^+	Soluble NO_3^-	Fixed NH_4^+
Control	Unlimed	88	14	523	61	7	506
	Limed	40	14	573	34	14	540
K	Unlimed	61	14	506	67	7	506
	Limed	34	14	573	27	14	557
Starch + K	Unlimed	27	14	506	54	7	489
	Limed	27	7	523	40	14	455
Rice straw + K	Unlimed	27	14	523	47	14	506
	Limed	27	14	573	40	7	540

When, however, no source of inorganic NH_4^+ -N was added to the soil, an increased amount of fixed NH_4^+ was observed in the limed over the corresponding unlimed soil (Table 1). This increase was attributed to the fixation of NH_4^+ produced through increased mineralisation of organic nitrogen in the soil. Since K^+ was added after the reactions leading to the increased fixation of NH_4^+ in the limed soil were over, it is quite obvious that in absence of NH_4^+ virtually no effect of added K^+ was observed in the limed soils. But much lower amount of fixed NH_4^+ was noticed in both the limed and unlimed soils when potassium is present simultaneously with

ammonium in starch added system (Table 2). Moreover, the said differential effect was more prominent in the starch added system than in the corresponding rice straw added soil. Starch as compared to rice straw furnished relatively higher amount of easily decomposable carbonaceous matter in the soil, thereby creating relatively higher amount of stress for available nitrogen in the soil which might have prompted the heterotrophic microbes to

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SIMULTANEOUS ADDITION OF K^+ AND NH_4^+ ON CHANGES IN THE AMOUNT (ppm) OF MINERAL FORMS OF N DURING INCUBATION IN LIMED AND UNLIMED SOIL, TREATED WITH STARCH OF RICE STRAW

Treatment material added to soil	Lime treatment	Amount of the forms of nitrogen in soil					
		5th. day			15th. day		
		Exch. NH_4^+	Soluble NO_3^-	Fixed NH_4^+	Exch. NH_4^+	Soluble NO_3^-	Fixed NH_4^+
Starch + NH_4^+	Unlimed	337	14	573	391	14	523
	Limed	162	20	500	34	7	489
Starch + NH_4^+ + K	Unlimed	344	14	506	351	7	455
	Limed	175	20	506	34	14	455
Rice straw + NH_4^+	Unlimed	432	14	573	364	14	540
	Limed	226	27	624	34	7	573
Rice straw + NH_4^+ + K	Unlimed	452	14	540	412	7	523
	Limed	250	14	607	40	7	557

utilise a considerable amount of fixed NH_4^+ resulting in a larger decrease of this fraction of mineral nitrogen in the starch treated soil than in the rice straw treated system. Irrespective of the nature of added organic matter, the inhibitory influence of added K^+ on the fixation of added NH_4^+ was noted on both the 5th. and 15th. day stages of sampling.

The observed effects on the fixation of added NH_4^+ due to the treatments adopted in the present investigation were not only found to be similarly effective on the amount of exchangeable NH_4^+ in the soil but also the magnitude of difference was of much higher order than that observed for fixed NH_4^+ (Table 2).

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